

VARIETY OF WAYS TO TEACH ARABIC LANGUAGE AS A SECOND-LANGUAGE LEARNERS. WISE SOLUTIONS TO COMMON WORLDWIDE TEACHING PROBLEMS.

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Abstract: Students who learn Arabic as a foreign language usually face difficulties to achieve proficiency in the language. This is because of the lack of Arabic authentic resources. However, there are a group of outstanding students who achieve fluency in Arabic by using their own methods. The effective methods used by outstanding students should be used as a guideline for other students to be more proficient in Arabic Language. In this article, the survey conducted in Malaysia can be a clear example and results from that research are written with useful steps of methods.

Key words: Arabic language, storytelling, religion, Semitic, lexical meaning, immersion, translation, pedagogical approach, presenting, acting, doing role play, survey, interaction, specialist, referring.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ АРАБСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЛЯ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АРАБСКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ИНОСТРАННОГО; ПРЕДЛАГАЕМЫЕ СТРАТЕГИИ КАК ДЛЯ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ, ТАК И ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ, ЧТОБЫ ПОЛУЧИТЬ ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ЗНАНИЯ

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Аннотация: Аннотация: Студенты, изучающие арабский язык как иностранный, обычно сталкиваются с трудностями при достижении уровня

владения языком. Это связано с отсутствием аутентичных ресурсов на арабском языке. Однако есть группа выдающихся студентов, которые свободно владеют арабским языком, используя свои собственные методы. Эффективные методы, используемые выдающимися учащимися, должны использоваться в качестве руководства для других учащихся, чтобы они лучше владели арабским языком. В этой статье обзор, проведенный в Малайзии, может быть ярким примером, и результаты этого исследования описаны с использованием полезных шагов методов.

Ключевые слова: арабский язык, рассказывание историй, религия, Семитский язык, лексическое значение, погружение, перевод, педагогический подход, презентация, игра, ролевая игра, опрос, взаимодействие, специалист, обращение.

ARAB TILINI XORIJIY TIL SIFATIDA O'RGANISH UCHUN ARAB TILIDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR; HAM O'QITUVCHILAR, HAM TALABALAR UCHUN AMALIY BILIM OLISH UCHUN TAKLIF ETILGAN STRATEGIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Arab tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganayotgan talabalar, odatda, tilni bilishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Buning sababi arabcha asl manbalarning yetishmasligidadir. Biroq, o'z usullaridan foydalangan holda arab tilini ravon o'rganishga erishadigan bir guruh ajoyib talabalar bor. Bilimli talabalar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan samarali usullar boshqa talabalarning arab tilini yaxshi bilishlari uchun qo'llanma sifatida ishlatilishi kerak. Ushbu maqolada Malayziyada o'tkazilgan so'rov aniq misol bo'lishi mumkin va ushbu tadqiqot natijalari foydali usullar bilan yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Arab tili, hikoya qilish, din, semit, lug'aviy ma'no, suvga solish, tarjima, pedagogik yondashuv, taqdim etish, harakat qilish, rol o'ynash, so'rov, o'zaro ta'sir, mutaxassis, murojaat qilish.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last 10 years, the Arabic language and the demand for learning it have increased significantly. The magic, the way of speaking and the charm of the Arabic language attract the attention of anyone at once. If someone learns this language for its charm and miracle, someone else will do it for educational purposes. Why has Arabic developed so rapidly in recent years?

There are reasons for this that have been studied worldwide.

Today, Arabic is one of the most widely spoken languages. In particular, the fact that Arabic differs from other world languages in tone, style, and pronunciation enhances its status and prestige in the world. Demand for Arabic and Arabic speakers are increasing day by day.

Arabic is a Semitic language originating from the Arabian Peninsula. When the Muslim World expanded, Arabic started to spread into Africa and Asia. The distribution of the Arabic language began within the seventh century throughout the Islamic conquests which expanded Arabic's reach from the Middle Eastern countries into Northern Africa. However, it took some time for Arabic language to blossom and prosper, since scientists and linguistics spent time on discovering words and terms.

Arabic is one of the oldest languages in the world with a wealth of knowledge that Archeologists to this day are still trying to discover and is the fifth most spoken world language. Roots of Arabic belonged to the sixth century. The Middle East has a rich storytelling history that has produced some of the most remarkable and famous stories such as the 'Arabian Nights', 'Ali Baba', and 'Aladdin'. Arabs have also made significant contributions in the areas of mathematics, navigation, astrology, architecture and so on.[1]

II. LITERARY REVIEW

Today Arabic is the official language of 26 Countries of the world and spoken by more than 280 Million people worldwide. Factually, one of the United Nation's Six official languages. (Chinese, Arabic, English, French, Russian and Spanish).

Here are some countries where the official language is Arabic: Egypt, Iraq, Israel, Kuwait, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen.

Let's explore why Arabic language is important to learn:

1. Language of Islam Religion

Arabic plays an integral role in the Islamic faith as Arabic is the language of the Holy Quran. Muslims appreciate the importance of Arabic language in very high esteem with most of their beliefs. Muslims consider Arabic as the divine gift and a sacred part of their customs. They perform five daily prayers in Arabic. Muslims believe that Arabic will be the mother of all languages in the world, is the very first language taught to Adam.

2. Business of Arabic

Arabic business is trying to break into foreign international markets. So learning that language opens opportunities to employment possibilities in the number of many industries like oil, finance, energy, translation and government.

3. Rising demand for Arabic

While Arabic is one the world languages, there are still very few Arabic translators available in the western world. Now there is a very high demand currently for more and more Arabic translators and interpreters are needed by government departments, agencies as well as corporations, organizations and even private sectors striving to enter the global arena.

4. Educational studies for Arabic Studies

Because of the high demand for people speaking Arabic, many of the world's governments and agencies are offering many scholarships and other opportunities for individuals, especially, students and teachers who are interested in learning Arabic .

5. Rich History of Arabic

Many Arab countries played a huge part in the advancement of architecture, navigation, astronomy, mathematics or literature. By speaking Arabic, it is easy to

be closer to the minds of some of the most important inventors and researchers of the whole world.[1]

General about Arabic

In the beginning, scholars struggled to define and form Arabic as a language, because Arabic language is the Semitic language spoken in a large area including North Africa, Arabian Peninsula, and other parts of the Middle East.

On the one hand, one can refer to the language of the Holy Qur'an as the ideal archetype whereas Classical Arabic closely approaches that language. Modern Standard Arabic that differs from Classical Arabic in stylistic and lexical considerations is commonly used in most publications from newspapers to novels and in formal broadcasts like news programs and political speeches.[2]

On the other hand, spoken varieties of Arabic differ from each other significantly. While some varieties tend to exhibit a number of common features, including the definite article *al- and the paradigmatic maf'ūl passive participle, these features are problematic in defining Arabic either because they are not found throughout all varieties of the language or because they can be found in other languages.

Arabic shows the fullest development of typical Semitic word structure. An Arabic word consists of two parts: the root - which generally includes three consonants and provides the basic lexical meaning of the word and then the pattern - which consists of vowels and gives grammatical meaning to the word. Thus, the root /k-t-b/ combined with the pattern /-i-a-/ gives kitab - 'book,' whereas the same root combined with the pattern /-a-i-/ gives katib 'one who writes' or 'clerk.' The language also makes use of prefixes and suffixes, which act as subject markers, pronouns, prepositions, and the definite article.

Verbs in Arabic stay regular in conjugation. There are two tenses in Arabic, and they are: the perfect, formed by the addition of suffixes, which is often used to express past time and the imperfect, which is formed by the addition of prefixes and

sometimes containing suffixes indicating number and gender, which is often used for expressing present or future time. Additionally, there are imperative forms, an active participle, a passive participle, and a verbal noun. Verbs in Arabic are inflected for three persons, three numbers such as singular, dual, and plural, and two genders. There are also forms for the passive voice. However, there is no dual form and no gender differentiation in the first person, and the modern dialects have lost all dual forms.

There are three cases - nominative, genitive, and accusative - in the declensional system of nouns; however, these cases have largely disappeared from the spoken dialects, and they are often omitted in spoken Modern Standard Arabic.[2]

Basically, there are some effective ways to learn Arabic, and each of these ways involves a different approach to language learning. These approaches may include learning through complete immersion, learning by translation, grammar-based learning, communication-based learning, and vocabulary-based learning.[3]

III. METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Students who learn Arabic as a foreign language in foreign countries usually face difficulties to achieve proficiency in the language or it takes a lot of time to be fluent in Arabic. This is mainly because of the lack of Arabic language resources, but this reason does not hamper the emergence of a group of intelligent students who achieve fluency in Arabic by applying their own methods.

Students who learn Arabic as a foreign language in a foreign country usually face difficulties to achieve proficiency in the language. This is primarily because of the lack of Arabic language resources. However, this situation does not hinder the emergence of a group of outstanding students who achieve fluency in Arabic by using their own methods. This study investigated the methods used by these students to be used as a guideline for other students. To collect the data, a set of questionnaire was developed from the Imitation Strategy Instrument introduced by Rosni Samah (2014). The questionnaires were distributed to 50 outstanding final year students

from the Arabic language department, Faculty of Major Languages, Islamic Science University of Malaysia. The results showed that effective strategies for learning Arabic language as a foreign language were gathering, enhancing and applying. The targets are new vocabulary and sentence. The tools to perform the strategies were Arabic materials and language activities. This study recommends that in learning Arabic language as a foreign language, the three methods mentioned above should be applied. The Arabic materials should be provided and language activities should be organized effectively.[4]

Many students who learn Arabic as a second language face a variety of challenges. And the reason for this can be interpreted differently. There are two main reasons for this: the first is the lack of textbooks and materials for learning Arabic, and the second is the lack of knowledge and skills of Arabic language specialists and their poor teaching methods.

The teaching and learning of Arabic language in Malaysia at this present moment is facing an enormous challenges. The main problem is the pedagogical approach usually employed by most Arabic language teacher who use the traditional method in teaching. According to the research conducted by Azhar et al. (2008) and Abdul Halim (2005) some Arabic language teachers prefer to use a teaching method which concentrates more teacher's role and has less students' involvement. However, it is obvious that some teachers rarely contribute to the student's achievement. That's to say, the problem can be originated from the students themselves. They are weak in their Arabic proficiency and also use the traditional method in learning Arabic. [4]

During the research it is explained that most students prefer to just sit and listen to the teacher in learning the Arabic language. Moreover, they feel afraid to speak and be involve in activities in the Arabic Language class. As a result, Syakirah (2004) found that students face difficulties in understanding the Arabic Language subject. However, Rosni b. Samah (2013) expressed that the weakness actually comes from the students' personality or passive attitudes. This attitude also can be

seen through the actions of the students during the class. It happens, because they rarely apply proper learning strategies and tactics.

IV. RESULTS

By contrast, there are groups of students who showed excellence in their Arabic Language experience; the survey conducted in Islamic Science University of Malaysia reveals that students had two main instruments in learning Arabic language and they are Arabic materials and language activities. The Arabic materials were text books, dictionaries, magazines, newspapers, advertisements, internet, cartoon materials, radio programs, TV programs, recorded materials, friends, teachers, and Arabic speakers. The language activities are reading, listening, interaction, and writing activities. The success of using those materials has been proven by many language specialists.

For these students, their goals were to memorize usually new vocabularies and sentences. To be successful, they have planned a way of learning method such as gathering, enhancing and applying. In implementing their way of learning, they had named the steps for each method.

No.	Steps	Targets	Activities	Materials
1	searching	New vocabulary and sentence	reading, listening	text books, dictionaries, magazines, newspapers, advertisements, internet, cartoon materials, radio programs, TV programs, recorded materials
			interaction	friends, teachers, and Arabic speakers
2	recording		reading, listening and interaction	text books, dictionaries, magazines, newspapers, advertisements, internet, cartoon materials, radio programs, TV programs, recorded materials, friends, teachers, and Arabic speakers
3	asking		reading, listening, writing and interaction	friends, teachers, and Arabic speakers
4	referring		reading, listening, writing and interaction	Dictionaries, friends, teachers, and Arabic speakers

As it can be seen from the table that the first step is called – ‘Searching’ and in this process doing reading and listening activities with the help of textbooks, publishing materials, internet and online resources is advisable in order to know new vocabulary and sentence structure. Next, doing recording, asking and referring activities with

the role of cartoon materials, radio and TV programs, teachers, friends and Arabic speakers.

In every language learning process happens with authentic materials and innovative materials, likewise, usage of Arabic material is considered as one of the tools to acquire new vocabularies and sentences. In gathering new vocabularies and sentences, outstanding students applied searching, recording, asking and referring methods to acquire new vocabularies and sentences.

To perform the four steps in gathering new vocabularies and sentences, the outstanding students used the language activities as a medium in learning Arabic language. The language activities provided opportunities for reading, listening, writing and speaking or interaction.

In order to apply the methods above, firstly, teachers and specialists should create an atmosphere for students to put the method into practice. Those methods can be seen in many types of exercises like:

- ✓ communicating,
- ✓ interacting,
- ✓ presenting,
- ✓ acting,
- ✓ doing role play,
- ✓ translating,
- ✓ writing,
- ✓ listening,
- ✓ reading in learning Arabic language.[5]

V. CONCLUSION

Overall, learning Arabic as a second language requires more effort from not only students, but also teachers. Applying methods into practice and doing activities in everyday learning do a lot for them. However, it is clear that the outstanding students have their own methods in learning Arabic language as a

foreign language, additionally, they build their own situations in acquiring the new language. Moreover, they possess their own methods and steps to be applied in language activities. Methods and useful steps can be a guideline for those who learn Arabic as a second language in far areas.

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